

European Researchers' Night 2024/25

D10.1 Management Report 2025

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1. | Executive Summary

This document presents an overview of the management and coordination activities carried out throughout the full duration (M1-M20) of the project **EU-EMBRACES (Empowering Minds: Boosting Research in Citizen Engagement and Schools)**, to ensure effective coordination and execution of the project. It consolidates the work conducted during both phases of the project—May 2024 to April 2025 (M1-M12) and May 2025 to December 2025 (M13-M20)—covering all ten Work Packages (WPs). These include awareness campaigns, activities associated with the European Researchers' Nights 2024 and 2025 and their respective build-up events, Researchers at Schools activities, impact assessment efforts, and the overall management of the project.

The report outlines the responsibilities and contributions of the consortium partners, including the coordinating institution, and describes the implementation of tasks across all WPs. It provides an integrated account of the work completed in both the first set of WPs (WP1-WP5) and their second-phase counterparts (WP6-WP10), highlighting progress achieved, deviations from the original plan when relevant, and the measures adopted to address challenges.

In addition, this summary reflects on the effectiveness of management strategies applied during the project and details how coordination mechanisms ensured coherent implementation across institutions and phases. It also presents the key outcomes of the project's activities, drawing from the final impact assessment to demonstrate alignment with the objectives of the MSCA & Citizens initiative.

Overall, this report offers a comprehensive overview of the project's execution from inception to completion, ensuring transparency, accountability, and a clear demonstration of how EU-EMBRACES fulfilled its goals over the twenty-month duration.

2. | Project and consortium overview

EU-EMBRACES was a Horizon Project aimed at fostering engagement and inclusivity in Science Communication, with a particular focus on reducing socio-economic disparities in access to science and innovation. Throughout its implementation, the project actively engaged underrepresented audiences, particularly those from disadvantaged socio-economic backgrounds, demonstrating how Horizon Europe Missions can positively impact their lives.

Implemented over a 20-month period (2024–2025), EU-EMBRACES successfully delivered two editions of the European Researchers' Night across nine venues in Portugal and implemented **300 activities nationwide**. These activities took place across continental Portugal and brought together researchers, schools, local authorities, non-governmental organisations, cultural institutions, and companies, fostering dialogue between science and society and strengthening territorial engagement with research and innovation.

The project was structured into two implementation phases (May 2024–April 2025 and May 2025–December 2025) and organised into ten Work Packages (WPs), distributed across the two phases and covering the project's core components:

- **Awareness campaigns** (WP1, WP6)
- **Activities during the main events** (European Researchers' Night 2024 and 2025) and **Build-Up activities** (WP2, WP7)
- **Researchers at Schools activities** (WP3, WP8)
- **Impact Assessment** (WP4, WP9)
- **Project Management** (WP5, WP10)

The EU-EMBRACES consortium comprised three main partners:

- **Ciência Viva – Agência Nacional para a Cultura Científica e Tecnológica**, the national agency for Scientific Culture and Technology;
- **i3S – Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde**, a research institute with strong expertise in education, public engagement, and health research;

- **ITQB NOVA – Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier**, a research and academic institution with extensive experience in science outreach and project coordination.

The project was coordinated by **ITQB NOVA**, which was responsible for WP5 and WP10 (Project Management 1 and 2). ITQB NOVA ensured the administrative, legal, financial, and contractual management of the project, established common methodologies and procedures across the consortium, monitored progress against timelines and objectives, and acted as the main interface with the European Commission.

ITQB NOVA also led WP4 and WP9 (Impact Assessment 1 and 2) and organised the main European Researchers' Night events for both the 2024 and 2025 editions at the Marina de Oeiras.

i3S led WP1 and WP6 (Awareness Campaign 1 and 2), overseeing the project's communication strategy, visual identity, awareness-raising actions, and national dissemination activities.

In addition, i3S organised the main European Researchers' Night events for the 2024 and 2025 editions at its campus in Asprela (Porto).

Ciência Viva was responsible for WP2 and WP7 (Activities during the Night 1 and 2), coordinating the implementation of activities during the European Researchers' Night and the Build-Up events for both editions. Ciência Viva also led WP3 and WP8 (Researchers at Schools activities 1 and 2), coordinating school-based activities and initiatives targeting underserved neighbourhoods and young audiences.

Furthermore, Ciência Viva ensured close collaboration with seven **associated partners** from the national Ciência Viva network, which played a key role in the project's territorial outreach and implementation: **Centro Ciência Viva de Braga, Centro Ciência Viva de Bragança, Centro Ciência Viva de Vila Nova de Foz Côa, Centro Ciência Viva de Alviela, Centro Ciência Viva de Estremoz, and Centro Ciência Viva de Lagos.**

Ciência Viva organized the main ERN events for the 2024 and 2025 editions at Pavilhão do Conhecimento in Lisbon, whereas each of the seven Ciência Viva Science Centres organized the main *ERN* event at their respective venues.

Finally, all partners and associated partners were responsible for organizing and implementing the build-up events of WP2 and WP7 (Activities during the Night 1, 2), as well as the activities of WP3 and WP8 (Researchers at Schools activities 1, 2).

3. | Overview of the work carried out

The activities of the EU-EMBRACES project were organised into ten work packages. Five work packages were implemented during the first phase of the project (M1–M12, from May 2024 to April 2025), while the remaining five were implemented during the second phase (M13–M20, from May 2025 to December 2025).

3.1. Work Packages Updates

Below is a list of the WPs and the work carried out in each of them.

Work Package 1 & Work Package 6: Awareness Campaign 1, 2

WP1 and WP6 focused on the communication and promotion of the European Researchers' Night (ERN) as a year-round concept, emphasizing science outreach through build-up events, "Researchers at Schools", and other activities. Special efforts were made to use online platforms to build connections with younger generations. The WPs aimed to maximise public participation, establish ERN as a recognizable brand, and highlight EU-funded research.

Progress report by task

Task 1.1. – Integrated Communication Plan and Web Tools:

A strategic communication plan was developed, along with brand identity guidelines and a media kit (logos, social media copy, press releases).

Social media accounts (Facebook, X, Instagram, YouTube, and TikTok) were either created or reactivated and managed to disseminate information effectively.

Task 1.2 – Online Platforms and Build-Up Activities:

A website with interactive features, including maps, booking systems, and a volunteer scientist pool, was developed and launched. While i3S managed the website's content, the consortium partners decided to host the site on Ciência Viva's server. This decision was based on Ciência Viva's expertise in managing multiple websites and their dedicated IT team, which could efficiently handle increasing demands.

Throughout the year, science communication activities, such as build-up events and 'Researchers at Schools' programs, were implemented to build momentum in preparation for the NIGHT.

Task 1.3 - Ongoing Communication:

Engaging content was created and shared on social media and websites to maintain public interest and visibility leading up to and following the NIGHT.

Updates, coverage of activities, and post-event communications were provided to sustain engagement and lay the groundwork for future editions.

Task 1.4 Publicity and Media:

TV and newspaper advertising campaigns were launched.

EU support for science was highlighted through "EU Corners" at main events, which showcased EU-funded research projects and Missions.

Detailed description of the work carried out and its impact was reported in the deliverables **DI.1 – Integrated Communication plan** and **DI.2 – Awareness campaign 2024**, delivered respectively in July and November.

Task 6.1 – Implementation of the Communication Plan and Brand Identity

The communication plan and brand identity developed in WPI were consistently implemented throughout the 2025 edition. Visual identity guidelines and communication templates were applied across all national and local materials, ensuring coherence between venues and channels. The media kit was reused and updated where necessary to support promotional actions across digital and print formats.

Task 6.2 – Online Platforms and Build-Up Promotion

The ERN website and social media channels were actively maintained as central communication tools, providing updated information on venues, programmes, and build-up activities. The website underwent an update of layout and content to better suit the needs of the communication and partners. Online communication supported year-round engagement, promoted build-up events, and facilitated access to information on the European Researchers' Night 2025. Social media content and website updates played a key role in building momentum towards the main event and supporting outreach to students, families, and educators.

Task 6.3 – Continuous and Post-Event Communication

Communication activities were sustained before, during, and after the European Researchers' Night. In the lead-up to the event, posting frequency increased to maximise visibility and audience reach. After the Night, extensive coverage was

produced to document activities, share results, and reinforce public engagement, while also supporting the continuity of the programme between editions.

Task 6.4 – Media Campaign and EU Visibility

A multi-channel media strategy was implemented, combining television advertising, press coverage, digital media, and regional promotion. National and local media partnerships significantly expanded visibility across Portugal. EU support for research and innovation was highlighted through EU Corners at main venues and the consistent display of EU and project branding, reinforcing the role of European funding and EU Missions in addressing societal challenges.

Detailed description of the work carried out and its impact was reported in the deliverables D6.1 – Awareness campaign 2025, delivered in October.

Work Package 2 & Work Package 6: Activities during the Night 1, 2

WP2 and WP6 focused on organizing the 2024 and 2025 edition of the European Researchers' Night (ERN) and its associated Build-up events, which fostered meaningful connections between researchers and the community. Co-designed with researchers, these events were implemented nationwide to ensure wide public participation, particularly targeting communities that typically have limited engagement with science communication.

Progress report by task

Task 2.1. – The theme of EU-EMBRACES NIGHT:

Across the nine venues, the public of the ERN had the opportunity to meet and interact with scientists from a variety of research fields, who shared their knowledge and the results of their investigations. Many activities centered on the EU Missions—Climate Change Adaptation, Cancer, Ocean and Waters, Climate-Neutral Cities, and Soil Deal for Europe. Other activities explored a broader range of scientific topics, highlighting the societal value of research.

Task 2.2. – Locations:

Events (Build-up activities and main NIGHTS) took place in streets, squares, public markets, beaches, theaters, monasteries, research centers, museums, and many other public venues across the country (including Alviela, Braga, Bragança, Vila Nova de Foz Côa, Estremoz, Porto, Lagos, Lisboa, and Oeiras), bringing science directly to the public, including underserved groups, through partnerships with municipalities. The Build-up events engaged over 280

researchers and attracted approximately 27,500 participants across 32 sessions.

Task 2.3 – NIGHT Activities:

The main NIGHT events involved approximately 5,000 participants and more than 500 scientists across nine cities and villages in Portugal. Over 230 activities were delivered, encompassing hands-on activities, workshops, exhibitions, science shows, demonstrations, competitions, games, escape rooms, speed dating with researchers, and astronomy observations. There were also virtual guided tours, stand-up comedy, music and dance showcases, tastings, and street art, providing very diverse and engaging experiences for attendees. EU Corners in each venue showcased EU-funded research and opportunities. Particular effort was made to engage communities that typically have limited access to science communication, including musicians and dancers from underserved neighborhoods, the Deaf community, individuals facing social and economic vulnerabilities such as deprivation, exclusion, and risk, as well as young students from vocational high schools specializing in communication. Events ran from 4:00 p.m. to midnight on September 27, 2024, with strong researcher-public interaction.

Task 2.4 – Mobilization of Researchers:

Around 780 researchers (between the build-up events and the main NIGHT event) were involved nationwide.

A detailed description of the build-up events and activities performed during the Night was reported in the deliverable D2.1 – Report on the activities during the NIGHT 2024, delivered in December 2024.

Task 6.1. – The theme of EU-EMBRACES NIGHT:

As for the 2024 edition, also in 2025 the public of the ERN across the nine venues, had the opportunity to meet and interact with scientists from a variety of research fields, who shared their knowledge and the results of their investigations. Many activities centered on the EU Missions—Climate Change Adaptation, Cancer, Ocean and Waters, Climate-Neutral Cities, and Soil Deal for Europe. Other activities explored a broader range of scientific topics,

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Task 6.3 – NIGHT Activities:

The main NIGHT events involved approximately 5,800 participants and around 800 scientists across nine cities and villages in Portugal. Over 200 activities were delivered, encompassing hands-on activities, workshops, exhibitions, science shows, demonstrations, competitions, games, escape rooms, speed dating with researchers, and astronomy observations. There were also virtual guided tours, stand-up comedy, music and dance showcases, tastings, and street art, providing very diverse and engaging experiences for attendees. EU Corners in each venue showcased EU-funded research and opportunities. Particular effort was made to engage communities that typically have limited access to science communication, including musicians and dancers from underserved neighborhoods, the Deaf community, as well as young students from vocational high schools specializing in communication. The European Researchers' Night events took place on 26 September 2025. On average, activities lasted approximately six hours, with durations at individual venues ranging from about three to thirteen hours. During this edition, two venues, Oeiras and Lisbon, were visited by the project officer from the European Research Executive Agency (REA), who had the opportunity to observe the events first-hand and engage directly with researchers, students, visitors, and members of the organising teams.

Task 6.4 – Mobilization of Researchers:

Between the build-up events and the main NIGHT event, around 800 researchers were involved nationwide (330 in the build-up and 800 in the ERN).

A detailed description of the build-up events and activities performed during the Nights 2025 was reported in the deliverable 7.1 – Report on the activities during the NIGHT 2025, delivered in November 2025.

Work Package 3 & Work Package 8: Researchers at Schools activities 1, 2

WP3 and WP4 have established connections between the research community, schools, and disadvantaged neighborhoods, fostering collaboration, promoting STEM

education, and addressing social inclusion. Activities have engaged students, underserved communities, and families through existing networks, including Ciência Viva Science Clubs, involving a total of 7,200 participants across Portugal.

Due to the academic calendar, school-based activities (such as the *Meet the Scientists* program and the Participatory Debates) mainly were concentrated in the 2024/2025 school year. For this reason, the progress report by tasks is grouped across the coupled WP3 and WP8.

Progress report by task

Task 3.1 & 8.1- Meet the scientist campaign:

Across 2024 and 2025, a total of 158 *Meet the Scientists* sessions took place, engaging 6,052 students aged 6 to 18 and involving 184 scientists. Of these, 74 sessions were held in person, while the remaining sessions were conducted online; together, they reached schools distributed across the entire country.

The sessions focused on EU Missions and beyond, aiming to promote STEM careers and inspire students and their families to participate in the upcoming ERN events.

Task 3.2 & 8.2.- Participatory debates:

We organized 18 participatory debates with 379 students aged 12 to 17 and 37 scientists, enhancing their debate skills and raising awareness about EU Missions.

Task 3.3 & 8.3. - Program for Social Inclusion through Science and Technology:

We organized 35 activities in disadvantaged neighborhoods, and 4 activities in schools with historically high dropout rates and retention challenges, engaging 685 participants and 58 scientists, with the aim of democratizing access to scientific knowledge and fostering active citizenship.

Task 3.4 & 8.4- Youth Ambassadors Program:

For the first edition of the NIGHT, we engaged 154 students from 9 different Clubes Ciência Viva in schools as collaborators during the event. These clubs, created through partnerships between research centers and schools, provide access to scientific practices and foster experimental learning. The participating students showcased their own research in their own stand during the first edition of the NIGHT at Marina de Oeiras.

For the second edition we organized 4 science communication workshops for students to enhance their participation in and organization of activities during

the 2025 ERN, where they led stands, and we involved 16 science clubs and 3 schools, for a total of 268 students, to deliver stands in the Lisbon, Oeiras, and Porto venues of the ERNs.

A detailed description of the Researchers at Schools activities carried out until December 2024 was reported in the deliverable D3.1 – Report on the researchers at Schools’ activities 2024, delivered in January 2025. The detailed description of the majority of the events of the Researchers at Schools activities during the course of 2025 was reported in the deliverable D8.1 – Report on the researchers at Schools’ activities 2025.

Work Package 4 & WP9: Impact assessment 1, 2

WP4 and WP9 focused on evaluating the impact of Build-up events, the European Researchers’ Nights, and the Researchers at Schools activities. A unified assessment strategy was developed and implemented locally by partners using diverse tools while ensuring ethical practices, privacy, and data protection. Results were analyzed to measure progress toward the project’s objectives and improve outreach efforts.

Progress report by task

Task 4.1. – Design of the Assessment Strategy:

A comprehensive assessment strategy was created, defining Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) aligned with six objectives: 1) raising awareness of science, 2) reaching underserved audiences, 3) promoting public engagement, 4) involving scientists, 5) showcasing EU-funded projects, and 6) organizing quality activities. The tools used included surveys (both paper-based and online), voting walls, show-of-hands voting, short reports, testimonies, and photographs.

Task 4.2. – Implementation of the Assessment Strategy

A decentralized approach was adopted for data collection across various locations. A document outlining the evaluation guidelines was created, and training was provided to the consortium partners and associated partners. Standardized templates were utilized, complemented by regular feedback sessions to ensure consistency while allowing for local adaptations.

Task 4.3. – Analysis of Results

Quantitative and qualitative data relative to all the activities held until December 2024 were analyzed using statistical and thematic methods.

Findings helped evaluate the project's impact, inform future improvements, and are summarized in the deliverable D4.2 – Impact assessment delivered in January 2025.

Also, the Deliverable D4.1 – Feedback to the EU Survey on the results of the European Researchers Night and on the Researchers at Schools Activities 2024 was delivered in October 2024.

Task 9.1 – Revision of the Assessment Strategy

The assessment strategy designed under WP4 was reviewed at the beginning of the second project phase. No substantial changes were required, as the originally defined methodologies, indicators, and tools had proven to be effective and robust during the first edition. Maintaining the same framework ensured methodological consistency and comparability of data across both editions of the project, enabling a coherent analysis of results over time.

Task 9.2 – Implementation of the Assessment Strategy

In continuity with Task 4.2, the assessment strategy was implemented across all activities carried out during the second phase of the project. An updated evaluation guidelines document was distributed to consortium and associated partners, incorporating clarifications and minor adaptations to better address partners' specific operational contexts and resource constraints. This approach ensured consistent data collection while allowing sufficient flexibility for local implementation.

Task 9.3 – Analysis of Results

Quantitative and qualitative data collected throughout the entire duration of the project were analysed using statistical and thematic methods. The analysis covered all project activities, including Build-up events, European Researchers' Night editions, and Researchers at Schools initiatives. The consolidated findings are presented in Deliverable D9.2 – Impact Assessment, delivered in December 2025, providing a comprehensive overview of the project's overall impact.

Also, the Deliverable D9.1 – Feedback to the EU Survey on the results of the European Researchers Night and on the Researchers at Schools Activities 2025 was delivered in October 2025.

Work Package 5 and Work Package 10: Management 1, 2

These work packages focused on ensuring the successful implementation of EU-EMBRACES activities, effective internal and external communication, and compliance with EU requirements. ITQB NOVA coordinated the project, monitored progress, and handled administrative and financial management tasks.

Progress report by task

Task 5.1. & Task 10.1 – Internal Communication Flows:

Regular online meetings, held at least once a month and more frequently as needed, ensured synchronization among partners. Communication was facilitated through emails, Zoom calls, a dedicated WhatsApp group, and a shared drive for collaborative document editing. A kick-off meeting (in 2024), an in-person consortium meeting (in 2025) and ongoing video conferences supported effective collaboration.

The tables below show the list of the online meetings (or, where specified, in-person meetings) held in 2024 and 2025, respectively.

Table 1 – Monthly online meetings of the consortium in 2024

Meeting	Date	Agenda topics
Kick-off meeting (Ciência Viva, i3S, ITQB)	29/05/2024	Project launch, objectives, and coordination.
Project meeting (Ciência Viva, i3S, ITQB)	13/06/2024	General updates and discussion of next steps. Communication strategy, ERN.
Project meeting (Ciência Viva, i3S, ITQB)	22/07/2024	Feedback on deliverable <i>D1.1 Integrated communication plan</i> .
Website meeting (Ciência Viva, i3S)	17/07/2024	Website development and content review, coordination.
Project meeting (Ciência Viva, i3S, ITQB)	08/08/2024	Ongoing project updates and coordination.

Impact assessment training (Ciência Viva and associated partners, i3S, ITQB)	11/09/2024	Online training and guidance for teams across the 9 venues. Presentation and discussion of assessment guidelines and tools.
ERN preparation meeting (Ciência Viva, i3S, ITQB)	18/09/2024	Status update, strategy discussions, and coordination for ERNs.
ERN debriefing (Ciência Viva, i3S, ITQB)	11/10/2024	Feedback on ERN events from September 2024. Status update on impact assessment and Researchers at Schools activities.
Year 1 Wrap-up Meeting (Ciência Viva, i3S, ITQB)	25/10/2024	Feedback on the deliverable <i>D4.1 Feedback to the EU survey on the results of the ERN and Researchers at Schools activities</i> . Update on <i>Meet the Scientist</i> program.
Project meeting (Ciência Viva, i3S, ITQB)	25/11/2024	Feedback on the deliverable <i>D1.2 Awareness campaign report for 2024</i> . Update on Participatory debates.
Project meeting (Ciência Viva, i3S, ITQB)	16/12/2024	Feedback on the deliverable <i>D2.1 Report on the activities during the Night 2024</i> .
(Ciência Viva, i3S, ITQB)	09/01/2025	Update Social inclusion through science and technology program, young

		ambassadors program point of situation.
(Ciência Viva, i3S, ITQB)	27/01/2025	Feedback on the deliverables <i>D3.1 Report on the researchers at Schools activities, D4.2 Report on impact assessment 2024, D5.1 Management report 2024.</i>

Table 2 - Monthly online meetings of the consortium in 2025

Meeting	Date	Agenda topics
Project meeting (Ciência Viva, i3S, ITQB NOVA)	12/01/2025	Discussion on the organization of the <i>SciComm workshop for young ambassadors</i> , review of upcoming milestones, and planning of the in-person consortium meeting.
Website meeting (Ciência Viva, i3S, ITQB NOVA)	18/02/2025	Proposal and discussion of website updates, including layout and content.
Project meeting (Ciência Viva, i3S, ITQB NOVA)	18/03/2025	Update on the organization of the <i>SciComm workshop for young ambassadors</i> and the in-person consortium meeting (scheduled for 28 May).
Project meeting (Ciência Viva, i3S, ITQB NOVA)	29/04/2025	Verification of milestone achievement related to debate scheduling by partners; review of progress on May milestones; update on the <i>SciComm workshop for young ambassadors</i> .

In-person consortium meeting at i3S, Porto (Ciência Viva, i3S, ITQB NOVA)	28/05/2025	Update of Project Management (ITQB), Communication (i3S), ERN activities and Build-up events (Ciência Viva), schools and neighborhood activities (Ciência Viva), Impact Assessment (ITQB), final discussion.
Impact assessment training Meeting (Ciência Viva Lisbon, Ciência Viva Lagos, Ciência Viva Bragança, Ciência Viva Alviela , i3S, ITQB NOVA)	10/09/2025	Online training and guidance for teams of the 9 venues on the ERN 2025 assessment process.
Project meeting (Ciência Viva, i3S, ITQB NOVA)	21/10/2025	Review of feedback on the ERNs across all venues, progress update on Deliverables D6.1 and D9.1 to be submitted by the end of October, scheduling of the consortium's final meeting.
Final consortium meeting (Ciência Viva, i3S, ITQB NOVA)	18/11/2025	Progress update of milestones, progress update on next deliverables to be submitted (D7.1, D8.1, D9.2, D10.1), status update on financial execution.
Project Meeting (Ciência Viva, i3S, ITQB NOVA)	18/12/2025	Last review of deliverables to be submitted (D8.1, D9.2, D10.1)

Task 5.2 & Task 10.2. – Internal Project Structure and Decision-Making:

ITQB NOVA oversaw progress monitoring, quality control, and budget compliance, as well as coordinated communication, assessment strategies, and dissemination plans. Work Package leaders were responsible for implementing tasks and reporting to the coordinator. Local venues, managed autonomously by Ciência Viva, enriched project quality through partnerships and alignment with project objectives. Decision-making was consensus-based, always reaching full agreement among all partners.

Task 5.3 & Task 10.3. – Communication with the European Commission:

ITQB NOVA ensured communication with the European Commission through regular deliverables, reports, and updates as needed.

This approach ensured the efficient management of activities, alignment with objectives, and collaboration among all partners and stakeholders.

3.2. Deviations from the plan, challenges and mitigation measures

Below follows a list of key challenges that we faced during the project, for each WP, and mitigation strategies employed to address these challenges.

WP1: Awareness Campaign 1

Overall, the plan and goals for WP1 were met, even if some communication and dissemination actions were deferred for implementation in WP6. Some issues were detected on the website, which are currently being addressed. The intended improvements will result in a reformulation of the website for the remainder of the project. Many of these issues were identified prior to the ERN 2024 main event. However, due to the short timeframe and intense workload, along with the necessity of maintaining an accessible website during this critical period of the project, we opted to gather insights and feedback during the event and then address these challenges. This year, we will focus on making the necessary changes and adaptations to improve user experience by the 2025 edition. This reformulation will be carried out in close collaboration between the communication team (i3S) and the hosting website team (Ciência Viva). As for social media management and content creation to feed it, further collaboration

must be fostered in this second leg of the project to ensure that all venues are properly featured and their activities promoted. To that end, it is crucial, however, that all of them engage more with the main event's account and provide the required material for the communication team to produce content that highlights the whole spectrum of activities and approaches EU-EMBRACES comprehends.

WP6: Awareness Campaign 2

Overall, the planned activities and objectives of WP6 were successfully achieved. Issues identified during the implementation of WP1, particularly those related to the project website, were systematically addressed during WP6. The website reformulation was carried out through close and effective collaboration between the communication team (i3S) and the website hosting team (Ciência Viva).

With regard to social media management and content production, enhanced coordination mechanisms were implemented during WP6 to ensure consistent visibility across all venues and adequate promotion of their respective activities.

In order to mitigate the limitations observed in the previous corresponding work package (WP1), additional person-months (PM) were allocated to WP6, contributing to improved performance and overall implementation quality.

WP2: Activities during the Night 1

The overall plan and goals for this work package were successfully met. Specifically, for the build-up activities, instead of the 27 initially planned for the first year, we successfully carried out 32 activities, exceeding expectations. As for the main NIGHT 1 events, everything proceeded as planned, without any significant deviations.

WP7: Activities during the Night 2

The work package objectives were successfully met. The number of build-up activities exceeded initial expectations, with 31 activities implemented compared to the 27 originally planned. The main NIGHT 2 events were carried out according to plan, without any significant deviations from the original schedule or format.

WP3: Researchers at Schools activities 1

Due to the academic calendar, school-based activities (such as the *Meet the Scientists* program and the Participatory Debates) only began in September 2024.

Consequently, we anticipated that the distribution of activities throughout the project's duration would be more concentrated during this school year (2024/2025). Indeed, all planned events were completed, even exceeding the expectations, by the end of the project (see WP8)as originally envisioned.

In addition, while the Youth Ambassadors programme initially planned to establish partnerships with *Ciência Viva* clubs during the first academic year in order to involve students primarily in the second ERN edition, existing collaborations, particularly between ITQB NOVA and several *Ciência Viva* clubs, enabled earlier and broader student participation, involving a total of 154 students. Consequently, student involvement in the first edition was nearly four times higher than originally planned, representing a significant positive deviation from the initial plan.

WP8: Researchers at Schools activities 2

As foreseen, the combined objectives of WPs 3 and 8 were successfully achieved and, in several cases, exceeded. A total of 158 *Meet the Scientist* activities were organised, surpassing the approximately 150 initially planned. Additionally, 18 participatory debates were implemented, compared to the 15 foreseen, while 39 *Social Inclusion through Science* events were carried out, closely aligning with the target of 40.

Furthermore, each partner delivered a science communication workshop aimed at Young Ambassadors students. These workshops resulted in the participation to the ERN 2025 of 16 science clubs and 3 schools, involving a total of 268 students.

WP4: Impact assessment 1

No significant changes were made to the planned methodologies or tools for impact assessment, and all evaluation processes were implemented as originally foreseen. A key operational challenge concerned the standardisation of data collection, particularly in light of the diversity of partners involved and the varying levels of available resources. This was addressed by adopting a flexible and supportive approach tailored to partners' needs, for example, providing assistance to smaller *Ciência Viva* Science Centres with the digitalisation of paper-based questionnaires and identifying alternative strategies to achieve comparable data quality with reduced financial resources.

Another area of attention concerned improving survey response rates among researchers, especially during large-scale events involving participants from multiple institutions, such as certain build-up activities and the European Researchers' Nights.

Experience showed that administering surveys on site, during the events themselves, led to higher response rates than post-event follow-up requests, and this approach was progressively prioritised.

Despite these challenges, impact assessment data were successfully collected for the vast majority of activities carried out.

WP9: Impact assessment 2

As in WP4, no substantial changes were required to the planned methodologies or tools for impact evaluation, and the assessment activities were implemented as foreseen. Particular attention continued to be given to the specific needs of partners, especially smaller Ciência Viva Science Centres, in order to ensure consistent data quality despite resource constraints.

A notable improvement was observed in researcher survey response rates during *Researchers at Schools* activities, where participation levels were approximately twice as high compared to large-scale public events. This is likely attributable to the smaller scale of these activities and the more direct engagement of researchers, who were not participating alongside large numbers of peers from different institutions.

WP5: Management 1

Overall, the management activities under WP5 have proceeded as planned, with no significant deviations or issues encountered. The established timelines, procedures, and coordination mechanisms have been successfully followed, ensuring smooth communication and collaboration among partners. No particular challenges have arisen, and the project management has remained effective in supporting the achievement of the project's goals.

WP10: Management 2

Management activities under WP10 continued in line with the approach and procedures established during the first phase of the project. Coordination, monitoring, and administrative processes remained effective throughout the final phase, ensuring continuity, compliance with contractual obligations, and timely completion of all activities and deliverables. Communication within the consortium remained regular and constructive, enabling the project to conclude as planned. No significant management-related challenges were encountered, and the management

framework successfully supported the project through its finalisation and reporting phase.

4. | Impact overview

Table 2 - Impact overview of EU-EMBRACES

Foreseen Impact (project as a whole)	State of the art at project conclusion	Additional information (if applicable)
Short-term result		
A set of activities and events involving researchers and lay-audiences, in particular young people, and underserved audiences;	<p>300 activities organized (111 in 2024 and 189 in 2025)</p> <p>63 build-up events; (32 in 2024 and 31 in 2025)</p> <p>18 ERN events; (9 in each edition)</p> <p>158 meet the scientists events; (57 in 2024 and 101 in 2025)</p> <p>18 participatory debates; (1 on which in 2024)</p> <p>39 Social inclusion through science and technology events; (12 in 2024 and 27 in 2025)</p> <p>184 actions specifically with young people; (43 in 2024 and 141 in 2025)</p> <p>40% of ERN participants were under 25 years old;</p> <p>47 actions specifically with underserved audiences;</p>	<p>Counts of actions targeting young people include only those within the Researchers at School activities. Build-up and ERN activities specifically directed at young people are not included, as a complete count was not available.</p> <p>Counts of actions targeting underserved audiences include Social Inclusion through Science and Technology events, as well as 4 ERN actions in 2024 and 4 in 2025 in Oeiras aimed at underserved audiences.</p>
A Youth Ambassadors network;	<p>154 students from science clubs were engaged to lead and facilitate activities during the 2024 ERN.</p> <p>106 students from science clubs received training in science communication to enhance their participation and organization of activities during the 2025 ERN, where they led stands.</p>	

	268 students led stands in 2025 ERNs.	
Many citizens across the country participating in science outreach activities;	Over 57,303 people participated in EU-Embraces science outreach events (of which 35,755 in 2024 and 21,548 in 2025)	Includes build-up events, the main NIGHT events, Meet the scientists campaign, Participatory debates, Social inclusion through science and technology, and Youth Ambassadors program.
Researchers from all scientific areas engaged in science outreach activities;	2,215 researchers involved (835 in 2024 and 1,380 in 2025) from research areas that include: Medical and Health Sciences - 34% Natural Sciences - 20% Exact Sciences - 11% Engineering & Technology - 19% Social Sciences - 8% Humanities - 4% Education & Communication - 3%	
EU Missions highlighted;	EU missions presented in 66% of the activities;	
Research institutions with more visibility.	68 scientific institutions involved in ERN (institutional participation);	
Mid-term outcomes		
Increase the proportion of the national population engaging with science, particularly among underserved audiences such as ethnic minorities, migrants, and socio-economically disadvantaged populations. We anticipate	Among the 4,281 surveys administered to participants of outreach events, (1,569 gathered in 2024 and 2,712 in 2025) 25% reported that this was their first time having direct contact with a scientist.	

<p>that creating new opportunities for citizens to encounter science will spark greater interest in science-related issues in the future, leading to broader participation in science outreach activities and venues;</p>	<p>Focusing exclusively on surveys from participants of the <i>Meet the Scientist</i> activities (out of 1,808 surveys), this percentage increases to 29%, with an additional 13% stating that they were unsure.</p>	
<p>By involving school students in science, we expect to break barriers they may have in considering research as a potential career, showing that science is not too complicated nor uninteresting. We aim to bring a new cohort of students, specially from minorities and underserved groups, to universities, and later on to scientific and academic careers.</p>	<p>7,376 students involved (3,410 in 2024 and 3,966 in 2025)</p>	<p>This figure includes only the students who participated in the Researchers at Schools activities - including the Meet the Scientists campaign, participatory debates, Social inclusion through science and technology events, and Youth Ambassadors program.</p> <p>To this number, students who participated in the build-up events and the European Researchers' Night (ERN) should be added, although only estimates are available: approximately 760 for the 2024 build-up events, 800 for ERN 2024, and 2,000 for ERN 2025.</p>
<p>By involving researchers in different types of science outreach initiatives, we contribute to improving</p>	<p>Number of researchers involved in outreach initiatives: 2,215</p>	

<p>their communication skills and giving them new perspectives on the public's concerns and opinions on their scientific topic.</p>	<p>(835 in 2024 and 1,380 in 2025)</p> <p>11% of researchers known to have participated in outreach activities for the first time</p>	
<p>Research centres and universities realise the importance of participating in science outreach activities that go beyond preaching to the choir and start considering new strategies for reaching underserved audiences.</p>	<p>68 scientific institutions involved (institutional participation);</p>	<p>A number of institutions proactively reached out to the organizing partners to express their interest in participating in the ERN.</p>

5. | Suggestions for future editions.

The implementation of EU-EMBRACES confirmed the growing scale, visibility, and societal relevance of the European Researchers' Night, while also highlighting structural challenges that accompany its success. As ERN continues to expand, the resources required to meet public expectations increasingly exceed those covered by project funding alone, making complementary support from municipalities, private partners, and volunteers essential, while EU funding remains the indispensable foundation that enables such leverage.

At the same time, the coexistence of multiple consortia organising simultaneous ERN events has, in some regions, led to fragmented communication efforts. Greater coordination among consortia, including cross-referencing and mutual visibility across communication channels, could strengthen national coherence.

Finally, impact evidence consistently shows that year-round engagement activities, particularly those involving schools, associations, and local communities, are more effective in reaching audiences traditionally distant from science. Future calls would therefore benefit from further supporting ERN as the culmination of a continuous, long-

term outreach programme rather than a stand-alone event, reinforcing its inclusivity and societal impact.

6. | Conclusion

As the EU-EMBRACES project has now concluded, the consortium successfully achieved all planned objectives and deliverables. Each partner completed their assigned tasks, ensuring that activities were implemented effectively, on schedule, and in full alignment with the work plan. Work Packages 1 (Awareness Campaigns 1 & 2), 2 and 7 (Activities during the Night 1 & 2), 3 and 8 (Researchers at Schools 1 & 2), 4 and 9 (Impact Assessment 1 & 2), and 5 and 10 (Management 1 & 2) were carried out as planned, with minor adaptations made to optimize implementation and ensure maximal reach and impact.

Throughout the project, the consortium demonstrated strong collaboration and coordination, leveraging the complementary expertise of all partners to foster public engagement and inclusivity in science communication. A central focus was addressing socio-economic disparities in access to science and innovation. By actively involving underrepresented communities—particularly students and citizens from disadvantaged socio-economic backgrounds—the project successfully illustrated the positive impact of Horizon Europe Missions on society.

The EU-EMBRACES project delivered substantial and tangible results, reflecting the consortium's commitment to its mission. Key achievements include:

- **63 build-up events** to create momentum and awareness;
- **18 European Researchers' Night (ERN) events**, engaging broad audiences;
- **158 Meet the Scientists events**, strengthening direct interactions between researchers and the public;
- **18 participatory debates**, promoting dialogue on critical scientific issues in students;
- **34 social inclusion through science and technology events**, ensuring outreach to underrepresented communities.
- **4 workshops** on science communication directed to Young Embassadors.

These efforts have resulted in impressive engagement metrics:

- **57,503 participants** actively involved in the project's activities;
- **2,215 researchers** participating in the initiatives;
- **432** Young ambassadors participating in ERNs.
- Media coverage across **37+ major channels**, including television and online publications;

- A strong digital presence, with **103,000 social media users** and **18,700 unique website visitors**.
- **39,363** people made aware of ERN by participating in build-up events.

With all activities now successfully completed, the EU-EMBRACES consortium can confirm that the project has fully achieved its objectives. The coordinated efforts of all partners ensured a high level of engagement, inclusivity, and impact across diverse audiences. By fostering direct interactions between researchers and the public, and by addressing socio-economic disparities in access to science, the project has contributed to empowering minds and promoting a more inclusive and accessible scientific landscape in Portugal and beyond.

The lessons learned and the strategies implemented throughout the project provide a strong foundation for future initiatives in science communication and public engagement, ensuring that the momentum generated by EU-EMBRACES can continue to inspire and inform upcoming European Researchers' Nights and related activities.